

FAILURE PREDICTION MODEL FOR NCF LAMINATES LOADED IN COMPRESSION AND THE EFFECT OF OFF-AXIS LOADING

Anton Shipsha¹, Magnus Burman² and Johan Ekh³

¹ Department of Aeronautical and Vehicle Engineering, KTH Royal institute of Technology
Teknikringen 8, SE-100 44 Stockholm, Sweden
Email: shipsha@kth.se, web page: <http://www.kth.se>

² Department of Aeronautical and Vehicle Engineering, KTH Royal institute of Technology
Teknikringen 8, SE-100 44 Stockholm, Sweden
Email: mburman@kth.se, web page: <http://www.kth.se>

³ Department of Technology Consulting/Applied Mechanics, ABB AB Corporate Research
Forskargränd 7, SE-72178, Västerås, Sweden
Email: johan.ekh@se.abb.com, web page: <http://www.abb.com>

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ABSTRACT

Design of reliable and efficient mechanical joints with non-crimp fabric (NCF) composites depends on accurate compressive strength prediction. Motivated by this, the current study is focused on the compression strength of NCF and the effect of fibre orientation in relation to the loading direction. Influence of stacking sequence on the compressive strength is studied as well. An experimental methodology is developed based on the classic IITRI test setup complemented with digital speckle photography (DSP) for accurate strain measurements. Compression tests of NCF composite laminates loaded at various off-axis angles are performed for different lay-ups. An engineering model for strength prediction of NCF composite laminates loaded in compression is suggested. Good agreement between the proposed model and the experiments was observed.

1. Introduction

Fibre reinforced composites are used increasingly in industry due to their high strength and stiffness combined with low weight. The ability to tailor material properties to meet mechanical and structural requirements specific for the particular application makes these materials attractive to use in highly demanding structural applications.

Aerospace industry pioneered the use of composite materials. Most defense aircrafts today have greater than 50% weight from composites. Composites have recently become a primary material for the new generation of commercial aircrafts such as the Boeing 787 “Dreamliner” (50%) and the Airbus A350 (53%). Composites used in aerospace industry have traditionally been produced from prepregs due to their excellent in-plane mechanical properties in terms of stiffness and strength. However, these materials are associated with high manufacturing costs. Another drawback of prepreg composites is sensitivity to out-of-plane loading. The use of an alternative type of reinforcement such as woven blankets can eliminate disadvantages found in conventional prepreg composites. Woven composites suggest benefits of relatively low production cost and increased out-of-plane strength, but the in-plane material properties are lower in comparison to prepreg composites.

A possible solution which combines high mechanical properties and lower manufacturing costs is a specific type of reinforcement structure called Non-Crimp Fabric (NCF). This type of textile preform has reinforcement in the form of blankets consisting of several layers stitched together by stitching yarns. The layers consist of highly directed, straight unidirectional fibre bundles. This type of reinforcement provides composites with in-plane properties comparable to those of prepregs, and considerably improved out-of-plane properties. Easy handling and manufacturing processes not requiring use of autoclave, e.g. Vacuum Infusion Process or RTM allow to significantly decrease manufacturing costs for NCF composites. NCFs have succeeded on the market due to their advantages and have displaced prepregs in such structures as: AIRBUS A380 rear pressure bulkhead; hull and deck of the Swedish Navy's Visby class corvette (a 72 m long vessel); wind turbine blades (more than 60 m) in wind power industry. New industry segments are looking more at these materials e.g. automotive, rail and truck.

Increasing demand on composites in structural applications brings the issue of mechanical joints to a new level of importance. Often the joint issue is the main technical challenge in introducing composites into new structural applications. Efficient joints rely on suitable material processing, design methods and quality control. An important issue in establishing design methodology for mechanical joints is accurate compressive strength prediction. This is motivated by the fact that local compression on the hole edge is identified as the initial failure mode for bolted/riveted joints.

Mechanical joint design methodologies and manufacturing processes are relatively well established for traditional prepreg composites. For fibre composite materials based on non-crimp fabrics (NCF), design methodologies are more sparse and need further attention. The main issue for improvement here concerns strength in compression.

Failure of laminated composites loaded in axial compression has been an essential research topic for several decades. However the physics of axial compressive failure is not determined completely. This is mainly caused by the complexity of involved failure mechanisms. Although a number of experimental studies on different materials revealed that kinking is a dominating failure mechanism in compression, the reasons for kink bands formation are not established 'officially'.

Literature study revealed two basic approaches to explain kink band formation. The first hypothesis suggested by Rosen [19] assumes kink band formation as the final result of micro buckling of the fibres elastically supported by the matrix. The second approach follows Argon's theory [1] considering initial fibre misalignment in the material which induces shearing stresses between the fibres that in turn causes further rotation of the fibre; then matrix failure triggers kink band formation. Schultheisz and Waas [20] [24] proposed that fibre micro buckling dominates for composites with very soft matrices, whereas for composites with stiffer matrices failure occurs through kinking triggered by matrix failure. However both approaches do not describe micromechanics behind the kinking but rather predict an event (micro buckling or matrix failure) causing kinking. Relatively recently micro mechanisms behind kink-band formation were studied by Gutkin et al. [13]. They performed compression tests on notched unidirectional and cross-ply carbon/epoxy specimens in SEM chamber. They found that micro cracks developed in the resin coalescing in splitting, causing shear band formation and fibre failure.

A number of models for compressive strength prediction associated with kink band formation were found in the literature. These models are based on either micro buckling (Rosen's approach) [19] or kinking by matrix failure (Argon's approach) [1]. The failure criteria by Budiansky [4] and Slaughter [21] following Argon's approach seem to have bigger prevalence than others. More recently, Dávila et al. [8] proposed a combination of Argon's approach [1] and Dávila's matrix failure criterion [9]. Essentially, Dávila et al. assumed a misaligned fibre area, and that further rotation will arise during compressive loading. They then compute the stresses in the updated misaligned frame and apply matrix failure criterion. This model demonstrated fairly well results of strength predictions in WWFE [14] [23].

Increased interest of NCF composites from industry caused extensive research on this material. A number of papers concerning mechanical properties of NCF composites have been published in the last decade. In general, in-plane mechanical properties of NCF based laminates are somewhere in between of those for equivalent woven preforms based systems and for prepregs [3]. Through-thickness mechanical properties of NCF composites were noted to be significantly higher in comparison to prepreg composites [22].

Micromechanical behavior and damage modes in NCF composites are found to be different from those in conventional prepreg composites [12]. The main reason for this is the specific reinforcement architecture of NCF composites causing heterogeneity of the material on the several scales: on the micro- macro-levels heterogeneity has the same nature as in prepreg composites and is associated with difference in fibre orientation between the layers and fibre-matrix microstructure within distinct fibre bundles; but on the meso-level distinct fibre bundles exhibit different degree of waviness and are separated by resin rich zones. Also the NCF layers are nesting to each other which results in partly integrated plies. Fibre tow waviness and fibre tow layer nesting are affected by the textile architecture, lay-up and manufacturing process which in turn means that mechanical properties depend on these parameters. Therefore testing of UD specimens for characterization of the in-plane mechanical properties, as is standard procedure for prepreg composites, is not applicable for NCF composites [11]. Instead, these mechanical properties for the lamina should be defined for the material configuration in which the lamina will be used.

Mechanical properties in compression for NCF composites have been studied less than for prepreg composites. Literature observation revealed only few studies on damage mechanisms in compression for NCF composites and similar for analytical strength prediction models. Compressive strength for NCF composites was reported to be significantly less (up to 35%) than for prepreg composites [3]. Asp et al. [2] experimentally found that compressive strength of NCF composites was only half of that in tension. Edgren et al. [11] performed experimental characterization of NCF composites subjected to combined compression and shear. They performed tests on quasi-isotropic $[0/90/45/-45]_{S3}$ carbon fibre/vinylester laminates. The specimens were loaded in compression at different off-axis angles (0, 5, 10, 15 and 20 deg), thereby changing the compressive/shear stress ratio. They found that formation of kink bands was the mechanism responsible for specimen failure for all off-axis angles; individual kink bands were found at loads significantly lower (typically 90%) than failure load for small off-axis angles (0 and 5 deg.).

Modeling of the NCF composites is not straightforward due to the complexity of the reinforcement structure. Two main modeling strategies for NCF composites were found in literature. The first strategy involves detailed modeling of the material architecture in finite element formulations [6, 7]. The second strategy is engineering models based on semi-laminar considerations (individual bundle layers can be represented as laminas in the laminate) which may be used in conventional laminate analysis schemes [11]. Detailed FE models are expensive and cumbersome since they require full material characterization. However engineering models require correct homogenization procedures of the material and knowledge about the in-situ lamina strength due to its dependence on the stacking sequence. Both modeling strategies are important and useful. However, engineering models provides a good starting point to study and understand the governing mechanisms.

Edgren et al. [11] proposed an engineering model for compressive strength prediction of NCF composites. The model is based on a semi-laminar approach and allows the criterion suggested by Slaughter [21] to be applied to homogenized laminas using CLT. However the influence of the remote transverse stress component was neglected in this model. Authors noted that further validation of the model is required for use in 3D stress state. The suggested model demonstrated good agreement with experiments on quasi-isotropic CFRP laminates loaded in compression at different off-axis angles. However the model was validated only for QI layup and needs further validation.

Literature study revealed insufficient experimental characterization of mechanical properties in compression for NCF composites. Thus no experimental study was performed on compressive strength of NCF composites with cross-ply layup. Influence of stacking sequence on compression strength also was not investigated. Existing engineering models for compressive strength prediction were validated only for a limited number of material configurations and require further validation.

Considering the high importance of accurate compressive strength predictions for NCF composites in structural applications, and found gaps in experimental characterization and analytical models for these materials, the objectives of the present study are:

- Experimental investigation of the compressive strength of cross-ply NCF laminates loaded at different off-axis angles.
- Experimental investigation of the effect of stacking sequence on compressive strength of quasi-isotropic and cross-ply NCF laminates.
- Identification of a strength criterion that can be implemented into analytical models for accurate compressive strength prediction of NCF laminates.

2. Experimental Procedures

NCF composite laminates of two different layups (quasi-isotropic and cross-ply) were tested in compression at different off-axis angles. All tests were conducted in accordance to the test standard ASTM D3410 [5]. Strength levels were determined for each off-axis angle.

2.1 Materials

The laminates were manufactured from T700 carbon fibres and Vinylester epoxy resin (DION 9102) by the vacuum infusion method. The type of NCF preform used for both laminate types was biaxial 0/90 tricot-chain stitched fabric Devold LT450 with a total areal weight of 430 g/m². The fabric was balanced and fibre layers in both directions had an equal areal weight. The stitch length was 2.5 mm.

The stacking sequences of produced laminates were [90/0/90/0]_s and [90/0/45/-45]_s providing cross-ply and quasi-isotropic laminates correspondingly. The thickness of the all laminates was 2mm. The overall fibre volume fraction was approximately 50%. The void content was not measured but from microscope investigations it was estimated to not exceed 1%. Properties of the material constituents are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Material properties.

Properties	Fibres	Matrix
E_L , longitudinal [GPa]	230	3.5
E_T , transversal [GPa]	20	3.5
ν_{LT}	0.3	0.3
G_{LT} [GPa]	20	1.2

2.2 Specimens preparation

Specimens were cut from the laminates at different off-axis angles. The number of specimens of each off-axis angle is presented in table 2.

All specimens were prepared in accordance to ASTM D3410 [5]. Specimen dimensions were: 16 mm X 140 mm (width X length). Specimens were cut using a diamond blade saw, with a precision of 0.1 mm. The edges of the specimens were sanded in order to eliminate damage introduced by the cutting procedure. End tabs were produced from woven glass fibre /epoxy composite and attached to the specimens end parts with epoxy Araldite 420 in such a way to leave a section of 12.5 mm in the center of the specimen. Flatness and parallelism of tabbed specimens were controlled according to the test standard.

2.3 Mechanical testing

The laminates were tested according to the test standard ASTM D3410 [5] with IITRI test set up. A scheme of the IITRI test set up is illustrated in the figure 1. Specimens prepared with end tabs are clamped in the clamping wedges and placed in the fixtures. Compressive load acting on the specimen is transferred by shearing between wedges from applied compression on alignment blocks.

The static compression tests were displacement controlled with constant speed of 0.5 mm/min. Tests were performed with an Instron electric testing machine with load capacity of 100 kN. During the test load was registered by standard load cell.

For the compression tests there is a problem of potential Euler buckling of the specimen. Gage length of specimens was chosen in accordance to specific requirements of ASTM D3410 [5] to eliminate possibility of Euler buckling. If the loading during compression test is eccentric it results in a combined compression and bending. In such case this can be detected by a difference between the axial strains on the back and front surfaces of the specimen. Test standard ASTM D3410 [5] recommends monitoring of longitudinal strains on opposite surfaces of the specimen by strain gages mounted back-to-back. In the present study, a digital image correlation (DIC) system was used to measure strains on the edge of the specimen.

Figure 1: Schematic and photograph of IITRI compression test fixture. The schematic was redrawn from figure 5 in ASTM D3410 standard [5].

2.4 Results

The results of the compressive tests are presented in Table 2 where compression strength values are calculated as the load at failure, divided by the specimen cross-section area. The distributions of the

compressive strength with off-axis angle for cross-ply and quasi-isotropic laminates are presented in figure 2 and figure 3 respectively.

For the cross-ply laminate (figure 2) a general trend is that compressive strength decreases with increasing off-axis angle. However, for small off-axis angles in the range of $[0; 5]^\circ$ failure stress seems to be unaffected. An influence of stacking sequence was found as well. The average compressive strength for 0° off-axis angle (giving $[90/0/90/0]_s$ stacking sequence) is 10% less than average compressive strength for 90° off-axis angle (giving $[0/90/0/90]_s$ stacking sequence). However, a significant scatter in the results was found for off-axis angles larger than 60° and it can be concluded that more testing is needed to verify the influence of stacking sequence.

For the quasi-isotropic laminate (figure 3) a strong influence of the stacking sequence was found. Comparing compressive strengths for 0° , 45° and 90° off-axis angles (giving $[90/0/45/-45]_s$; $[-45/45/0/90]_s$ and $[0/90/-45/45]_s$ stacking sequences, respectively) the highest value of 345 MPa corresponds to 45° off-axis angle; 330MPa was the strength for 90° off-axis angle, whereas 0° off-axis angle specimens had strength of 255 MPa.

Figure 2: Effect of the off-axis loading on the compressive strength of cross-ply NCF laminate.

Figure 3: Effect of the off-axis loading on the compressive strength of quasi-isotropic NCF laminate.

Table 2: Experimental results.

Laminate type	Off-axis angle	Number	Strength [MPa]	Standard dev [MPa]	σ_L [MPa]	τ_{LT} [MPa]
Cross-ply	0°	9	357.8	34.0	-662.5	0
	5°	6	378.9	15.9	-696.1	32.9
	10°	6	289.3	18.1	-519.1	49.5
	15°	5	213.3	14.5	-368.0	53.3
	20°	11	172.8	15.9	-281.9	55.6
	45°	3	119.8	3.9	-108.7	59.9
	60°	4	146.3	3.8	-201.8	63.3
	70°	3	184.4	20.4	-300.8	59.3
	80°	3	288.8	10.9	-518.4	49.4
	85°	3	401.4	38.2	-737.5	34.9
	90°	4	401.7	76.7	-743.8	0
Quasi-isotropic	0°	8	257.0	12.3	-671.7	0
	20°	6	267.4	16.3	-592.0	16.7
	45°	5	343.1	15.1	-896.5	0
	70°	3	297.6	14.1	-658.8	18.6
	90°	4	327.4	8.4	-855.5	0

3. Strength prediction.

Literature observation revealed that the criterion suggested by Edgren et al. [11] is the most appropriate and the most verified engineering model for compressive strength prediction of NCF composites existing today. The model is based on a semi-laminar approach substituting individual bundle layers with laminas. This approach allows performing stress analysis of the NCF composite using classical lamination theory (CLT). Strength prediction in the model is based on a rearranged version of the criterion proposed by Budiansky and Slaughter [21] predicting kink band formation. The suggested model demonstrated good agreement with experiments [11]. However the model was verified experimentally only for quasi-isotropic laminates subjected to combined compression and shear loading and needs further validation if to be used with cross ply laminates.

Expression (1) derived by Budiansky and Slaughter represents the response of a kink band in a rigid-perfectly plastic material subjected to remote loading by axial compressive stress σ_x ; shear stress τ_{xy} and transverse stress σ_y . In expression (1) τ_y is the shear yield strength of the rigid-perfectly plastic solid, β is the kink band angle, φ_0 is the initial fibre misalignment, φ is the additional fibre rotation caused by the remote loading, $\alpha = \sqrt{1 + R^2 \tan^2 \beta}$, $R = \sigma_{Ty} / \tau_y$, where σ_{Ty} is the yield stress in pure transverse tension. This criterion is to be applied on micro-scale of the material within the bundle in its local coordinate system following the crimped fibers. Edgren et al. rearranged expression (1) assuming linear interaction between the stress components acting on the bundle in order to use the criterion in the lamina coordinate system and arrived at expression (2).

$$\sigma_x^\infty = \frac{\alpha \tau_y - \tau_{xy}^\infty - \sigma_y^\infty \tan \beta}{(\varphi_0 + \varphi)} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\sigma_L}{\sigma_{c0}} + \frac{\tau_{LT}}{\tau_{LT0}} = 1 \quad (2)$$

In Eq. (2) σ_L and τ_{LT} are the stresses acting on the NCF composite lamina; σ_{c0} and τ_{LT0} are the uniaxial compressive strength and shear strength of the NCF lamina material respectively. The strength parameters must be determined from tests on the NCF composites of the same stacking sequence as that of the analyzed laminate. Measurement of these parameters in the tests of the isolated individual laminas is not applicable due to the strong influence of internal architecture and manufacturing processes on the mechanical properties in NCF composites. The influence of the remote transverse strength is neglected in Eq. (2).

Semi-laminar consideration requires correct homogenization treatment of meso-scale heterogeneity in the form of bundle waviness. This can be performed using the stiffness reduction model for NCF composites proposed by Edgren and Asp [10] where wavy bundles are represented by curved Timoshenko beams.

In the present study, the model described in [11] was applied to predict strength of the tested cross-ply and quasi-isotropic NCF laminates. Following Edgren and Asp [10], knock-down factors were applied to longitudinal modulus E_L of homogenized laminas calculated by a micromechanical approach. In their investigation knock-down factors were estimated using information on the actual bundle geometry. However in this study knock-down factors were chosen to be 0.9 as the value corresponds to a typical NCF composite structure for all bundle layers in both laminates [10]. Longitudinal compressive strength of the NCF lamina σ_{c0} was measured in compression tests with the fibres of the investigated laminas parallel to loading direction. The pure shear strength of the NCF lamina τ_{LT0} was determined for both laminate types in the same in-plane shear test performed in compression of the cross-ply laminate with 45° off-axis angle as it was suggested by Edgren et al. in [11]. Knowing the experimentally defined failure load for each specimen type the stresses in the most highly loaded laminas were calculated using CLT (Table 2) and compared with predicted values.

As expected the model could predict strength of the off-axis loaded quasi-isotropic laminate fairly well. This is verified by a small experimental series shown on the figure 4 where stress state at failure loads for the 20° and 70° off-axis tests is presented together with criterion lines (eq. 2). In the plots on figures 4(a) and 4(b) three different criterion envelopes correspond to different values of compressive strength σ_{c0} obtained from compression tests.

Figure 4: Stresses at failure in the most highly loaded lamina of the quasi-isotropic laminate and Failure envelope according to Eq. (2) for 20° off-axis angle (a) and 70° off-axis angle (b)

However prediction for the cross-ply laminate was far from experimental data. The stress state at failure of the off-axis loaded cross-ply laminate and criterion envelopes using eq. (2) (plotted as a dashed line) are represented in figure 5. It can be seen that compressive strength of the cross-ply laminate is largely underestimated by the criterion.

Figure 5: Stresses at failure in the most highly loaded lamina of the cross-ply laminate and Failure envelope according to Eq. (2) for off-axis angles in the range of [0; 20] (a) and [60; 90] (b)

The possible reason for the poor predictions with cross-ply laminate originates from the inaccurate determination of the strength parameters σ_{c0} and τ_{LT0} . As it was described above σ_{c0} values were retrieved from the compression tests of the laminates with fibers parallel to loading direction and τ_{LT0} was obtained from in-plane shear test. However longitudinal compressive strength of the NCF lamina σ_{c0} is underestimated by this method. This can be explained by the fact that suggested model simplistically considers plane stress state in NCF bundle instead of fully volumetric stress state caused by out-of-plane waviness. In turns it means that the effect of all neglecting stress components on compressive failure load is virtually included into the values of compressive and shearing stresses σ_L and τ_{LT} (eq (2)). This substitution is reasonable for tests with sufficient off-axis angles where the in-plane shear stress in NCF lamina is large enough to be comparable with out-of-plane shear stress in NCF bundle. However for 0° off-axis test in absence of the in-plane shear stress in NCF lamina the effect of the -of-plane shear stress in NCF bundle can be significant. Also Edgren et al. noted in [11] that the strength criteria in eq. (2) being based on the linear compression–shear interaction requires that the failure mechanism is kinking in all cases including the pure shear. Therefore the shear strength parameter τ_{LT0} obtained from the pure shear test as it was outlined previously cannot be used in the criterion since the failure mechanism is not kinking. Actually measurement of the pure shear strength τ_{LT0} parameter for the criterion is not straightforward because there is no available test method to fulfill this requirement.

Edgren et al. recommended in [11] to derive strength parameters σ_{c0} and τ_{LT0} from extrapolation of the linear fit through the strength results achieved in off-axis compression tests. In [11] this method was applied to tested quasi-isotropic laminates and provided longitudinal compression strength of approximately 10% higher in comparison to the value obtained from the 0° compression test. The extrapolated shear strength was approximately 6% lower than the value retrieved from in-plane shear test. In the present study this method was applied to the tested cross-ply laminate. A linear fit to the off-axis test data was performed and extrapolated to the axes as shown in figure 6. Strength parameters values were determined by crossing points of the fit line and axes. Longitudinal compression strength and shear strength values were found to be: 1310 MPa and 77 MPa for linear fit through 5°, 10°, 15° and 20° off-axis test data; 1450 MPa and 74 MPa for linear fit through 60°, 70°, 80° and 85° off-axis test data. The linear fit approximation method provides σ_{c0} and τ_{LT0} values significantly higher (approximately on 96% and 24 %) than values obtained from corresponding tests.

It can be seen that the compressive strength of the NCF lamina obtained by linear fit approximation method are much larger for the cross-ply laminate than for the quasi-isotropic. The possible reason for this is that the cross-ply laminate in 0° off-axis test is more sensitive to small shear stresses induced by out-of-plane waviness. It is important to note that linear fit approximation method gives some ideal

strength values of the NCF lamina allowing to apply the criterion in eq. (2) for laminate loaded with off-axis angle but not corresponding to the real strength of the 0° NCF laminate.

Figure 6: Linear fit approximation and Failure envelope according to Eq. (2) for off-axis angles in the range of $[0; 20]$ (a) and $[60; 90]$ (b)

From engineering point of view failure envelope for cross-ply laminate can be obtained by cut-off of the linear fit approximation line to the horizontal axis at the point corresponding to some certain off-axis angle as it shown in figure 7. The value of this angle depends on the sensitivity of the failure load to small shear stresses caused by out-of-plane waviness as discussed above. In order to get exact value of the angle the model needs in further development to allow consideration of the volumetric stress state in a bundle.

Figure 7: Cut-off of the linear fit approximation for off-axis angles in the range of $[0; 20]$ (a) and $[60; 90]$ (b)

4. Summary and conclusions

In the present study the effect of off-axis loading on compressive strength was experimentally studied in cross-ply NCF laminates. It was found that compressive strength decreases with increasing off-axis angle, however for small off-axis angles in the range of $[0; 5]^\circ$ failure stress seems to be unaffected.

An influence of stacking sequence was experimentally studied on cross-ply and quasi-isotropic laminates. For the cross-ply laminate the average compressive strength for $[90/0/90/0]_s$ configuration was found to be 10% less than average compressive strength for $[0/90/0/90]_s$. However, additional testing is required to verify this due to a significant scatter in the test results for off-axis angles larger than 60° . For the quasi-isotropic laminate the average compressive strengths for $[90/0/45/-45]_s$ and $[0/90/-45/45]_s$ configurations were found to be 95% and 73% of the average compressive strengths for $[-45/45/0/90]_s$ configuration.

Available engineering model for compressive strength prediction of NCF composites [11] was applied to predict strength of tested laminates. The model demonstrated good agreement with test results for both laminates. However the model was found to be needed in further development.

5. Future work

Experimental results of cross-ply laminate demonstrated significant scatter of compressive strength values for off-axis angles larger than 60° . Therefore additional tests are required in order to verify experimental results and drawn conclusions.

Fractography on tested laminates is to be performed in order to determine fracture mechanisms governing failure and damage progression.

Development of the engineering model allowing compressive strength prediction of NCF cross-ply laminates as small off-axis angles and describing volumetric stress state in fiber bundles is to be performed.

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